

PRODUCTIVITY INDICATORS OF BREAD WHEAT SAMPLES STUDIED IN THE CONDITION OF FERGANA REGION

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ABSTRACT

In the article, research was conducted in order to create a new variety of bread wheat with stable productivity adapted to the conditions of Fergana region. During the studies, when the productivity indicators of wheat were studied, the plant height was 92.6-106 cm, the number of spikes was 16.67-20.67, the weight of the spike was 1.77-2.21 g, the weight of 1000 grains was 38.2-43.2 g, and the yield was 4.54-6.79 t/ha.

In plant science, there are more than 90 cultivated crops that considered to be necessary for humans. Grain crops are one of the most important crops among these plants, and flour, bread and macaroni products are made from their grain. Cereal farming, especially the production of abundant crops from grain crops, is one of the areas of strategic importance in the agriculture of our country.

In Uzbekistan in creating the best varieties of bread wheat, grain structure and its quality indicators, external circumstances and agrotechnical actions strongly affects to the wheat quality. It is significant to study grain yield of winter wheat in the soil-climate condition. In cereal farming it is appropriate to use high-yield varieties in order to increase grain yield.

In the experimental field of the institute's Baghdad branch, Fergana region, a competition nursery was established, and

researches were carried out by planting 14 samples and 1 check variety in 3 replications, each cutting on an area of 10 m². According to the results of the conducted research, the varieties studied in Fergana region were not significantly different from the statistical point of view in terms of days to spike ($R>0.294$), days to full ripening ($R>0.247$) and spike length ($P>0.138$). 1st table

Since different groups of agricultural crops have different reproductive biology, morphological characteristics and directions of economic use, it is important to know the main direction when conducting analysis processes. Among the important directions in grain growing are the period of spike-ripening and productivity indicators [2].

In terms of the height of the plant stem was 102 cm, in other varieties the lowest index was 92.67 cm and the highest index was

105.33 cm in 2 samples KB-20-YT-IR 9808 and KB-20-YT-IR 9812. We observed that sample KB-20-YT-IR 9808 is resistant to lodging. Of course, it leads to decrease the harvesting. Number of spikes was 16.67-20.67 and weight of spikes was 1.77-2.21 gr. Big difference was not observed between spike weight and weight of 1000 grains. In experiments weight of 1000 grains in sample and varieties consisted 38.2-43.2gr.

In the research carried out in Fergana region, the productivity of the model variety was 4.54 t/ha, and it was found that all the samples gave a higher yield than the model variety, and this was proven in the results of statistical analysis. The analysis showed that wheat samples KB-20-YT-IR 9816, KB-20-YT-IR 9842 and KB-20-YT-IR 9812 were found to have a stable yield. It was found that wheat samples KB-20-YT-IR 9808 and KB-20-YT-IR 9820 yielded equal or less than the model variety.

1st table. ANOVA statistical analysis according to vegetation period and biometric indicators in bread wheat varieties in Fergana region

No	Genotypes	DTH	DTM	PH	PL	SL	NSS	SW	TKW	PY
1	BEZOSTAYA 100 (check)	156	207	102	34.67	9.33	16.67	1.92	39.37	4.54
2	KB-20-YT-IR 9808	162	204	105.33	37	9.67	16.67	1.77	41.17	4.98
3	KB-20-YT-IR 9812	159.7	209	105.33	38	12	20.33	1.87	43.23	6.34
4	KB-20-YT-IR 9815	159.7	207	105	37	10	19.67	2.12	41.63	5.05
5	KB-20-YT-IR 9816	159.3	206.7	103.33	35	10.33	20.33	1.93	41.1	6.79
6	KB-20-YT-IR 9818	162	209	102	43.67	10	19.33	2.11	40.83	5.72
7	KB-20-YT-IR 9820	163.7	206.7	97.67	33	11	18.67	1.97	40.67	5.33
8	KB-20-YT-IR 9825	160.7	206.3	106	35	10.67	19.33	2.0	41.03	5.57
9	KB-20-YT-IR 9829	161.3	207.3	95.67	33	9.67	18	1.95	40.97	5.43
10	KB-20-YT-IR 9841	159	206.7	96	29.67	10	16.67	2.21	38.93	4.76
11	KB-20-YT-IR 9842	161	207	90.67	29.33	10.33	18.67	1.89	41.77	6.08
12	KB-20-YT-IR 9843	151.7	195.3	92.67	30.33	10	17	1.84	38.2	5.74
13	KB-20-YT-IR 9846	160.3	208	93.33	30	9.67	17.33	2.12	41.47	5.38
14	KB-20-YT-IR 9847	160	205.3	92.67	35.67	8.33	17.33	1.81	41.2	5.33
15	KB-20-YT-IR 9821	159.3	206.7	93.67	31	11.33	20.67	1.84	41.93	5.93
	P (>F) 0.05 %	0.294	0.247	<.001	<.001	0.138	0.013	0.023	<.001	<.001
	LSD_{0.05}	3.2	8.1	6.714	5.7	1.99	2.577	0.14	1.643	0.43
	CV	2.70	2.35	4.06	9.98	11.72	8.35	1.14	2.40	4.65

Samples and varieties of bread wheat in the condition of Fergana region 4 samples which have high-productivity indicators

were selected and recommended to continuing the researches in the future levels of selection.

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